

Aerodynamic barriers to inhaled furosemide delivery during dyspnoea revealed by experimental and computational modelling

Frantisek Lizal^{1*}, Miloslav Belka¹, Zdenka Sklubalova³, Ondrej Misik¹, Jakub Elcner¹, Michal Svarc⁴, Ludmila Matysova², Vladimir Koblizek⁴

¹Brno University of Technology, Faculty of Mechanical Engineering, Energy Institute, Technicka 2896/2 Brno, 616 69, the Czech Republic

²Charles University, Faculty of Pharmacy, Department of Analytical Chemistry, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

³ Charles University, Faculty of Pharmacy, Department of Pharmaceutical Technology, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

⁴ University Hospital Hradec Kralove, Department of Pulmonology, Hradec Kralove, Czech Republic

*Corresponding author: Frantisek Lizal, lizal@fme.vutbr.cz

Abstract:

Inhaled furosemide shows potential for relieving refractory dyspnoea, yet clinical trials have yielded inconsistent results. We hypothesise this failure stems from a "Dyspnoea Paradox", where high inspiratory flows create an aerodynamic barrier. We evaluated furosemide delivery using a vibrating mesh nebuliser under simulated dyspnoeic conditions (tidal volume 1.39 L, frequency 28.6 min⁻¹). The study integrated standard Pharmacopoeial characterisation, in vitro deposition in a realistic human airway replica, and computational modelling (Large Eddy Simulation and Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry). While standard tests indicated optimal aerodynamic properties (MMAD 3.03 µm), realistic modelling revealed a critical barrier. Both experimental and computational results showed excessive deposition in the upper parts of the airways, caused by a "Laryngeal Jet" that increases inertial impaction and turbulent dispersion. Standard Pharmacopoeial methods thus yield false-positive predictions of delivery efficiency for dyspnoeic patients. We conclude that rapid inhalation associated with air hunger filters out a significant portion of the therapeutic dose before it reaches the target tracheobronchial receptors. Clinical strategies must therefore shift from dose escalation to flow-governed delivery or shape-optimised carriers to overcome this aerodynamic filtration.

Highlights:

- Inhaled furosemide efficacy is limited by aerodynamic filtration during dyspnoea
- Standard Ph. Eur. methods fail to predict drug delivery under dyspnoeic conditions
- 3D models reveal lobar deposition hotspots missed by MPPD predictions
- High inspiratory flows create a laryngeal jet, causing increased throat deposition
- Targeting airway receptors requires flow control, not dose escalation

Keywords: Dyspnoea, inhaled furosemide, vibrating mesh nebuliser, airway model, computational fluid dynamics, drug delivery

1. Introduction

Dyspnoea represents one of the most prevalent and distressing symptoms in internal medicine, significantly impacting patients' quality of life. It constitutes a major source of global morbidity in subjects with advanced cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Despite advances in palliative medicine, a safe and effective therapeutic strategy for refractory dyspnoea remains elusive [1,2].

Dyspnoea is defined by the American Thoracic Society (ATS) as "a subjective experience of breathing discomfort that consists of qualitatively distinct sensations that vary in intensity" [2]. Unlike objective clinical signs, the subjective nature of dyspnoea means that the patient's perceived distress does not necessarily correlate with measurable physiological parameters such as blood gas levels. Neurophysiologically, the symptom is postulated to arise from an "efferent-afferent mismatch", i.e., a dissociation between the central motor command output to respiratory muscles and the incoming afferent feedback from pulmonary mechanoreceptors.

Inhaled furosemide (FUR) has emerged as a potential therapeutic candidate for the management of refractory dyspnoea. While primarily indicated for the oral and/or intravenous treatment of heart failure and oedema, evidence from case reports and randomised controlled trials newly suggests a beneficial effect of inhaled FUR on dyspnoea in both healthy volunteers and patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [3–5].

Although inhaled FUR may induce mild bronchodilation by stabilising epithelial membranes [6], the primary mechanism of action is hypothesised to be neurophysiological [4,5]. Inhaled FUR is believed to sensitise Pulmonary Stretch Receptors (PSRs), specifically the Slowly Adapting Receptors (SARs) [7], localised within the smooth muscle of the conducting airways (generations 2–16). By lowering the firing threshold of these mechanoreceptors, inhaled FUR amplifies the afferent neural signal of lung inflation transmitted via the vagus nerve. This enhanced signalling mimics the feedback of a larger tidal volume, thereby reducing the abovementioned efferent-afferent mismatch and attenuating the perception of air hunger [8].

Despite this physiological rationale, clinical efficacy data remain inconsistent. While some studies report significant relief, others utilising high-dose protocols failed to demonstrate a therapeutic effect [9]. We hypothesise that this heterogeneity might stem from inter-subject variability in aerosol deposition sites. Given that SARs are anatomically restricted to the tracheobronchial tree, successful delivery to this specific region is a prerequisite for drug efficacy. Consequently, alveolar deposition is therapeutically ineffective, while larger extrathoracic deposition represents a loss of the active pharmaceutical ingredient.

Notably, the majority of prior clinical studies failed to characterise the aerodynamic particle size distribution (APSD) or the regional deposition of the administered aerosol. Consequently, the lack of therapeutic response in some cohorts may be attributed to delivery failure rather than a lack of pharmacological efficacy. This issue highlights a broader challenge in respiratory drug development: the exceptionally high attrition rate of drugs during clinical trials [10]. This paper aims to demonstrate that advanced computational and experimental modelling represents a crucial tool to bridge the gap between standardised preclinical testing and clinical outcomes.

A critical limitation in the assessment of inhaled therapeutics is the reliance on standard Pharmacopoeial methods (Ph. Eur.) [11], which employ standardised testing regimes and fail to replicate the dynamic breathing patterns of a dyspnoeic patient. Subjects experiencing severe

dyspnoea exhibit elevated inspiratory flow rates and rapid acceleration. From a fluid dynamics perspective, inertial impaction is governed by the Stokes number (Stk), which is proportional to the flow velocity and the square of the particle diameter, $Stk \propto U \cdot d^2$. Therefore, the pathological increase in inspiratory velocity directly elevates the Stk significantly increasing the probability of inertial deposition in the oropharynx. Furthermore, these high-flow conditions promote the formation of a "Laryngeal Jet", a high-velocity turbulent flow structure that significantly enhances the inertial impaction and turbulent dispersion in the upper parts of the tracheobronchial tree [12]. This phenomenon creates a "Dyspnoea Paradox", wherein the physiological manifestations of the symptom itself generate an aerodynamic barrier that impedes aerosol delivery to the target tracheobronchial region.

The objective of this study is to quantify aerodynamic barriers for inhaled medication using inhaled FUR as a model case. We combined standard Pharmacopoeial characterisation with *in vitro* measurements in a realistic human airway replica and Large Eddy Simulation (LES) to analyse regional deposition under simulated dyspnoeic breathing conditions. This approach allows for the assessment of whether therapeutic aerosol can effectively reach the SAR-rich lower tracheobronchial airways despite the aerodynamic challenges imposed by the pathological breathing pattern.

2. Results

2.1. Compatibility of the VMN with the Preparation

The compatibility study revealed a minimal difference in pH values between the commercial FUR Kabi 20 mg/2 mL product (8.20 ± 0.01) and the same FUR preparation after nebulisation (8.21 ± 0.01). The average FUR content after nebulisation was $101.4 \pm 6.94\%$ compared to the original commercial preparation; no decomposition products were observed in the HPLC chromatogram. These results confirmed that the Aerogen Solo VMN did not alter the chemical properties of the FUR preparation during the 20-minute nebulisation and is fully compatible with this medicinal product.

2.2. Delivered Dose

The dose of FUR delivered to the patient, determined using the standard Pharmacopoeial method, was 21.03 ± 2.92 mg. This represents $52.57 \pm 7.31\%$ of the initial dose filled into the nebuliser. This reduction is expected, as the breathing simulator alternates between inspiration and expiration, meaning the aerosol generated during the expiratory phase is not inhaled but vented. The total nebulisation time for 4 mL of FUR preparation (2 ampoules) ranged between 20 and 30.5 minutes, resulting in a mean dose delivery rate of 0.87 ± 0.35 mg·min⁻¹.

However, under the simulated dyspnoea breathing conditions (used in the *in vitro* deposition study described in Section 2.6), the inhalation time is significantly shorter than during standard testing, despite the nebulisation rate remaining constant. This resulted in a lower effective delivered dose rate of 0.39 ± 0.15 mg·min⁻¹. This indicates that the delivered dose rate may decrease by more than 50% during realistic dyspnoeic breathing compared to standard testing conditions due to the significantly different I:E ratio.

2.3. Aerodynamic Particle Size Distribution

The APSD, measured using the ACI, demonstrated excellent repeatability (Figure 6). The MMAD of the generated particles was 3.03 ± 0.03 μm. The GSD was 1.8 ± 0.01 , and the estimated FPF was $81.2 \pm 2.8\%$. These values indicate that the particles have the potential to effectively penetrate beyond the upper airways and deposit in the deeper parts of the lungs under standard resting breathing

conditions. However, to obtain accurate information on regional deposition under pathological conditions, data from airway replicas or computational simulations are required (see Methods).

Figure 1: The mass aerodynamic particle size distribution of nebulised FUR preparation given by the Andersen cascade impactor with 7 stages.

2.4. MPPD Modelling Predictions

The probabilistic basis for comparison was provided by the MPPD Model (Section 2.5). Under the specific dyspnoeic boundary conditions (tidal volume 1390 mL, frequency 28.6 min^{-1}), the model predicted a Total Deposition Fraction of 62.3% for the entire respiratory tract. The regional deposition breakdown was as follows:

- Head (Extrathoracic) Deposition: 29.6%
- Tracheobronchial (TB) Deposition: 23.8%
- Pulmonary (Alveolar) Deposition: 8.9%

It is important to note that the MPPD simulation modelled a standard breathing cycle (inspiration followed by expiration), predicting that 37.7% of inhaled particles would be exhaled. This contrasts with the *in vitro* and CFD methodology, which utilised a breath-hold protocol to force sedimentation.

2.5. Aerosol Deposition in Airway Replica (Experiment vs. CFD)

The comparison of deposition fractions measured experimentally in the airway replica and using CFD LES is depicted in Figure 7. Generally, good agreement was observed between the methods. The total deposition fraction in the replica (generations G0–G7) was 53.8% in the experiments and 66.2% in the LES simulations.

The highest discrepancy was observed in the upper airways. For example, deposition in the oral cavity (Segment 1) was 14.9% in the experiments compared to 22.8% in the simulations. The deposition fraction in the trachea (Segment 2) showed better agreement, with 3.5% detected in experiments versus 4.3% predicted by simulations. The total amount of deposited matter that penetrated beyond

the upper airways (i.e., deposited in Segment 3 and downwards) represented 81.6% of the recovered dose in the experiments, compared to 72.9% in the simulations.

Figure 2: The comparison of deposition fraction in the airway replica obtained by experiment (EXP) and by CFD simulations. Error bars represent standard deviations.

Lobar Deposition Distribution

As shown in Table 1, the distribution of the deposition fraction (DF) was not strictly proportional to the distribution of airflow during inspiration. For instance, the Right Middle Lobe (RML) received only 6.2% of the deposition in the CFD simulations despite receiving 10% of the flow, whereas experimental results showed 10.7% deposition. Conversely, the Right Lower Lobe (RLL) showed excellent agreement between methods.

Table 1: The comparison of deposition fraction (DF) distribution in lobes obtained by experiment (EXP) and by CFD (LES) simulations.

Lobes (segments)	Flow rate share (%)	DF EXP (%)	DF-CFD (%)
LLL (6,14,15)	21	13.1	13.1
LUL (7, 13,16)	25	14.6	12.1
RUL (9, 19,21)	21	15.4	11.9
RML (11, 17,20)	10	10.7	6.2
RLL (12, 18,22)	23	16.9	17.2
Sum	100	70.7	60.6

2.6. Comparative Lobar Deposition in G4 and Downwards (EXP vs. CFD vs. MPPD)

While a direct comparison of absolute total deposition is confounded by the breath-holding protocol used in the experiment versus the single inhalation in MPPD, the relative distribution of the deposited mass among the lung lobes provides interesting insight into the aerodynamic behaviour.

To enable this comparison, the analysis focused on generations 4 and downwards, which corresponds to the anatomical definition of distinct lobes in the MPPD (Yeh & Schum) [17] model. The MPPD data were postprocessed to account for the exhaled fraction, using the assumption that the airborne particles remaining after the first inhalation (i.e. predicted to be exhaled) would eventually deposit proportionally to the initial distribution during the breath-hold period.

Figure 8: Comparison of the lobar deposition fraction distribution of particles obtained by experiment (EXP), and simulations by CFD (LES) and MPPD. Error bars represent standard deviations of experimental results.

The results (Table 2) reveal a distinct disparity in the upper lobes. Both the experimental and CFD (LES) results show significantly higher deposition in the Left Upper Lobe (LUL) and Right Upper Lobe (RUL) compared to the MPPD prediction. For instance, in the RUL, the experimental deposition (13.9%) is more than double the MPPD prediction (5.6%). In contrast, the RLL shows remarkable agreement across all three methods. Note that MPPD in the standard Yeh & Schum [17] model uses a different distribution of flowrates than our experimental and CFD case.

Table 2: The comparison of deposition fraction distribution in lobes (generations ≥ 4) obtained by experiment (EXP), CFD simulations, and MPPD modelling.

Lobe (Segments)	Flow rate share (EXP and CFD) (%)	Flow rate share (MPPD) (%)	DF-EXP (%)	DF-CFD (%)	DF-MPPD (%)
LLL (14,15)	21	31	10.0	9.3	11.7
LUL (13,16)	25	16	12.2	9.3	4.7
RUL (19,21)	21	15	13.9	10.5	5.6
RML (17,20)	10	8	9.4	4.6	2.7
RLL (18,22)	23	31	15.6	15.6	13.7
Sum	100	100	61.1	49.4	38.4

3. Discussion

For successful drug delivery to the lungs, achieving an optimal particle size is a prerequisite. The optimum aerodynamic particle size range between 0.5 and 5 μm [27] is readily provided by modern application devices, such as the VMN used in this study [28]. However, even with an appropriate particle size distribution, the active substance may not reach the deeper parts of the respiratory tract, because inhalation drug delivery is conditioned by the synchronisation of breathing and aerosol formation [29]. Hence, detailed studies should always be performed to quantify drug losses in the upper respiratory tract and to determine the correct effective dose [30] before launching any inhalation system to clinical trials. This study combined *in vitro* measurements and numerical modelling to investigate these losses under specific dyspnoeic conditions.

A primary objective of this study was to evaluate the predictive power of different modelling approaches for inhaled furosemide delivery under dyspnoeic conditions. It is crucial to note that a direct comparison of absolute total deposition fractions between the physical replica and the MPPD model (Yeh and Schum [17]) is constrained by their geometric and methodological differences. The MPPD model simulated the entire respiratory tract (up to the alveoli) under a standard breathing cycle. In contrast, the physical and CFD models were anatomically truncated at the 7th generation and utilised a breath-holding protocol.

The comparison between experimental data and CFD simulations (Figure 7) showed generally good agreement, although CFD slightly overpredicted deposition in the extrathoracic regions (66.2% vs. 53.8%). This overprediction of CFD-determined deposition in the upper airways has been observed in other studies. Koullapis et al. [31] suggested that one reason can be the modelling of turbulence in the near-wall region, which can be mitigated by implementing corrections to velocity fluctuations [32]. From an experimental perspective, the large airways (oral cavity, trachea) pose a challenge for rinsing; these segments are too large to be immersed in liquid and must be rinsed manually, potentially introducing minor variability.

However, when comparing the relative lobar particle distribution within the conducting airways (generations 4–7), significant mechanistic differences emerge. The MPPD model, which relies on idealised branching, underestimates deposition in the upper lobes compared to both the experiment and the 3D CFD simulations (Table 2). The discrepancy between our CFD/experimental results and MPPD predictions regarding lobar deposition can be explained by the ventilation distribution assumptions. Standard MPPD simulations utilising Yeh & Schum [17] morphometry typically assume lobar ventilation proportional to lobar volume (i.e. assumes the uniform expansion). However,

physiological data demonstrate that ventilation is often heterogeneous and not strictly proportional to FRC volume. This is explicitly demonstrated by Kuprat et al. [33], who combined CFPD and MPPD models. In their subject-specific analysis, the RUL accounted for 33% of the lung volume at FRC but received only 20% of the inhaled flow. Conversely, the RLL accounted for only 24% of the volume but received 31% of the flow. Similarly, in our study, the 3D CFD simulation captured the inertial dynamics of the flow, which directed a higher fraction of the aerosol into the upper lobes than would be predicted solely by their volumetric proportion used in 1D dosimetry models. Therefore, the MPPD model seems to underestimate the deposited dose in the upper lobes by distributing the airflow according to lobar volume rather than local aerodynamics.

Based on our experimental data, we propose a mechanistic explanation for the inconsistent clinical efficacy of inhaled furosemide observed in previous trials [9,34]. The results reveal that under dyspnoeic breathing conditions (mean inspiratory flow $\sim 3.3 \text{ L}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), the upper airways act as a highly efficient filter, capturing 20 to 30% of the administered dose. We identify this phenomenon as the "Dyspnoea Paradox". The physiological state of air hunger drives the patient to breathe with high velocity and rapid acceleration. This significantly enhances the inertial deposition in the upper airways and also creates a powerful laryngeal jet, a turbulent flow structure extending from the trachea to the upper parts of the bronchial tree. This jet increases inertial impaction and turbulent dispersion not just in the larynx (where MPPD predicted $\sim 30\%$ deposition), but also in the proximal bronchial generations. Consequently, the very symptom requiring treatment (dyspnoea) generates an aerodynamic barrier that filters out a significant portion of the therapeutic aerosol before it can reach the distal conducting airways.

The neurophysiological hypothesis posits that FUR efficacy depends on sensitising SARs located in the smooth muscle of the tracheobronchial tree (generations G2 – G16) [7]. While SARs are distributed throughout these generations, the therapeutic contribution of the proximal airways (G2–G7) is limited by two factors: their relatively small surface area and the phenomenon of localised saturation. Under dyspnoeic flow conditions, inertial impaction concentrates the drug into specific 'hotspots' (bifurcations) within G2–G7. This likely leads to receptor saturation in these focal areas, while failing to utilise the extensive surface area of the distal conducting airways (G8–G16), where the drug could recruit a significantly larger population of SARs. Thus, generations G8–G16 represent the accessible and most effective target region. Hence, our data challenge the traditional metric of Total Lung Dose. For this specific therapy:

- Alveolar deposition is pharmacologically ineffective as SARs are absent in the respiratory zone.
- Oropharyngeal deposition represents a significant loss of drug due to the "Dyspnoea Paradox".
- Distal tracheobronchial deposition (generations G8 – G16) represents the true target region, which is difficult to reach under high-flow conditions.

The lack of a linear dose-response relationship in clinical studies can be attributed to aerodynamic saturation. Increasing the nebuliser charge under dyspnoeic flow conditions likely increases the mass impacting the upper parts of the airways without sufficiently increasing the dose delivered to the distal airways, where SAR density is high.

This study highlights the inadequacy of standard Pharmacopoeial measurements for predicting clinical outcomes in dyspnoeic patients. The ACI data indicated an MMAD of $3.03 \mu\text{m}$ and an FPF of $>80\%$. Under standard testing conditions ($28.3 \text{ L}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, laminar flow), these values imply excellent lung delivery. However, our realistic modelling shows that under the turbulent regime of dyspnoea, even these "optimal" $3 \mu\text{m}$ particles possess sufficient inertia to impact the throat and primary bronchi. The

standard methods, therefore, generate a false positive prediction of delivery efficiency by failing to replicate the patient's pathological breathing pattern.

Our results show that the Aerogen Solo VMN is fully compatible with the commercial FUR formulation and does not affect its stability. Therefore, the bottleneck is not the chemical composition, but the aerodynamics of administration.

For clinical practice, this implies that simple dose escalation is an ineffective strategy. To overcome the laryngeal jet and bypass the proximal impact zones, delivery strategies must address the increased inertial forces. In the context of current liquid nebulisation therapy, optimisation is limited to flow-governed delivery (e.g., breath-actuated nebulisers releasing aerosol only during the low-flow phase or coached breathing manoeuvres) and reducing the droplet size to compensate for the elevated Stokes number. However, liquid droplets are inherently spherical due to surface tension. To further exploit aerodynamic benefits, future therapeutic development could shift towards solid-state formulations, where anisotropic particle shapes (e.g., microrods) or magnetic guidance can be engineered to bypass the laryngeal filter [35,36].

The development of inhaled therapeutics is a complex and resource-intensive process, estimated to cost over \$1.5 billion and taking approximately 12 years from discovery to market entry [37]. Notably, the attrition rate is particularly severe for respiratory drugs, with a cumulative probability of reaching the market of only 3%, compared to 6–14% for other disease areas [10]. Our findings suggest that this high failure rate may be partially attributed to the reliance on inadequate preclinical testing methods (such as standard ACI or the Next Generation Impactor) that fail to detect aerodynamic barriers like the laryngeal jet. If a drug shows excellent fine particle fraction *in vitro* but fails in clinical trials due to throat deposition (as observed with high-dose furosemide [9]), the cost of failure is immense. Implementing realistic aerodynamic modelling—combining physical replicas and CFD—early in the development pipeline offers a crucial tool to bridge this gap, potentially identifying ineffective delivery systems before they enter costly clinical phases.

Several limitations of this study must be acknowledged. First, the study utilised a realistic but rigid geometry representing a single subject. Consequently, it does not account for inter-subject anatomical variability or the dynamic airway compliance observed *in vivo*. During the rapid inspiration characteristic of dyspnoea, dynamic airway collapse could alter the flow field, potentially increasing central deposition beyond our predictions.

Furthermore, to maintain consistency with standard Pharmacopoeial methods (ACI), the experiments were conducted at 5 °C without simulating evaporation or condensation. In a clinical setting, the warm and humid environment of the lungs (37 °C and 100% relative humidity) could induce hygroscopic growth of the droplets. This increase in particle size would likely further enhance inertial impaction, thereby reinforcing the "Dyspnoea Paradox" filtering effect described in this study.

It should also be noted that the 3D models (experiment and CFD) were anatomically truncated at the 7th generation. Therefore, deposition in the target region (G8–G16) was not directly measured but inferred from the fraction passing through the outlets or modelled using 1D dosimetry (MPPD), which lacks the resolution of 3D flow structures. Finally, the LES simulation slightly overpredicted deposition compared to the experiment (66.2% vs 53.8%). This discrepancy is likely attributed to the "trap" boundary condition, which neglects droplet bounce or splashing on the wet airway surface, and the breath-hold protocol used to force sedimentation, which does not fully replicate the exhalation phase of a respiratory cycle.

This study integrated experimental cascade impaction, realistic *in vitro* airway replication, and advanced computational modelling to characterise the delivery of inhaled furosemide under conditions of severe dyspnoea. Based on the results, we draw the following conclusions:

1. **Formulation suitability:** The Aerogen Solo vibrating mesh nebuliser is chemically compatible with the alkaline furosemide preparation, delivering a consistent aerosol with a high fine particle fraction (>80%) and maintaining the stability of the active substance.
2. **The "Dyspnoea Paradox":** We quantified the aerodynamic barrier created by the patient's condition. High inspiratory flow rates typical of dyspnoea cause a significant increase in the inertia of inhaled particles. Our realistic models (experiment and LES) demonstrated that this phenomenon transforms the upper airways into a highly efficient filter, capturing a significant portion of the dose before it can reach the lower airways.
3. **Targeting efficiency:** The neurophysiological target for dyspnoea relief, the SARs, resides primarily in the smooth muscle of the tracheobronchial tree (generations 8–16). Our data suggest that under uncontrolled dyspnoeic breathing, the target region (distal conducting airways) is difficult to reach due to substantial losses in the oropharynx and main bronchi, while alveolar deposition represents pharmacologically ineffective waste.
4. **Methodological implications:** Standard Pharmacopoeial measurements (Ph. Eur.) performed at constant low flow rates fail to capture these inertial effects, leading to a "false positive" prediction of delivery efficiency. Furthermore, 1D dosimetry models (like MPPD) may underestimate localised deposition hotspots in the upper lobes caused by the 3D complexity of the laryngeal jet.
5. **Clinical recommendation:** The observed lack of linear dose-response in clinical trials is likely a consequence of aerodynamic saturation rather than pharmacological inefficacy. Future clinical strategies should not focus merely on increasing the nominal dose, but on flow-governed delivery strategies. Implementing breath-actuated nebulisers, coached breathing manoeuvres, or size and shape optimised particles to reduce peak inspiratory flow is essential to bypass the laryngeal filter and maximise engagement with SARs.

This multi-modal modelling approach provides a mechanistic explanation for previous clinical failures and offers a robust platform for optimising future inhaled therapies for refractory dyspnoea.

4. Materials and Methods

Three methodological approaches were employed to characterise the properties of the inhalation system and assess the deposition and transport of inhaled particles within human airways. Following the core hypothesis of this study, a series of experiments using the Aerogen Solo vibrating mesh nebuliser (VMN) and an aqueous solution of FUR were conducted. First, the delivered dose and APSD according to the methods described in Ph. Eur. (2.9.44) were assessed. This was followed by the calculation of the dose delivered to various regions of the airways using the MPPD model. Subsequently, *in vitro* deposition measurements using a physical replica of the human respiratory tract (male geometry, oral cavity to the 7th generation of branching) and a programmable breathing simulator were performed. Finally, computational simulation of the inhalation within the digital twin of the airway replica was performed. These experimental and computational methods were compared to assess their potential to realistically estimate the local deposited dose and provide caretakers with better information about the behaviour of the inhalation system in real patients.

4.1. Nebuliser Selection and Confirmation of FUR Compatibility

Patients suffering from respiratory diseases need fast and efficient therapy, particularly in acute cases. This need is generally fulfilled by inhalation of medication in the form of aerosols administered to the

lungs using a suitable device, such as a nebuliser. Among the available nebuliser types, VMNs, which produce an aerosol by extruding the medication through a vibrating mesh, represent the preferred choice [13]. VMNs have several advantages, including a low residual volume, high nebulisation rate, and precise particle size definition governed by the mesh aperture, ensuring a high fine-particle fraction.

FUR substance was obtained from Fagron, Czech Republic. Water for injection (WFI) was used as a solvent throughout the whole study. All samples were always protected from light during manipulation and storage. Nebulisation was performed using the VMN Aerogen Solo (Aerogen Ltd., Galway, Ireland). To assess the compatibility of the VMN with the FUR solution, 4 mL of the commercial aqueous injection preparation FUR Kabi 20 mg/2mL (2 ampoules) were poured into the Aerogen Solo nebuliser chamber.

The produced aerosol was collected in a cooled glass tube covered with aluminium foil (Figure 1) for 20 minutes (the expected time of inhalation therapy). The FUR content was estimated by High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC). The pH value of the solution before and after the nebulisation test was measured using a pH-meter Sentron SI400 with a MicroFET pH electrode (Sentron Europe B.V., Leek, Netherlands). Three repetitions were carried out, and the average and standard deviation (SD) were calculated. The results were compared with the FUR content and pH value of the commercial preparation to ensure that no deviations of physical and chemical properties took place during the laboratory procedures.

Figure 3: Experimental setup for confirmation of FUR compatibility with VMN

4.2. Reagents and Analytical Method

FUR Impurity A (FUR A) was obtained from the Council of Europe – EDQM, Strasbourg, France. Methanol CHROMASOLV® gradient grade, acetonitrile (ACN) CHROMASOLV® gradient grade, formic acid 95%, and triethylamine (TEA) 99.5% were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich, Czech Republic. 18 MΩ.cm ultrapure water was obtained from a Milli-Q® Integral water purification system with a 0.22 µm Millipack® output filter (Millipore, USA).

The chromatographic analysis was used for the determination of FUR in the samples; FUR A was used to detect chemical degradation. A UHPLC system Liquid Chromatograph - Nexera X2 (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) with online detection using a diode array detector (SPD-M30 A) was used. The chromatographic system consisted of two quaternary pumps (LC-30 AD), a degasser (DGU-20A5R), an autosampler (SIL-

30AC), a column oven (CTO-20AC), a communication bus model (CBM-20A), and computer software (LabSolution). A reversed-phase LiChrospher column, 5 μm , C18 100 \AA , 125 x 4 mm (Phenomenex, USA) was used for the separation.

The mobile phase was prepared by mixing the buffer solution and ACN in a ratio of 75:25 (v/v) and adjusted to a pH of 5.75. The buffer solution was prepared by mixing 200 mL of water, 50 μL of formic acid, and 150 μL of TEA. Before use, the aqueous phase was filtered through a 0.22 μm nylon membrane filter. Analytes were eluted using a flow rate of 1.5 mL min^{-1} . A volume of 10 μL of the standard and sample solutions was injected every 2.5 minutes; the analytes were detected at 270 nm. A standard solution was prepared by dissolving the substances in methanol to reach the final concentrations of 50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for FUR and 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for FUR A. The standard solution was protected from light and stored at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the dark for a maximum of 24 hours.

The analytical method was validated according to ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines (ICH Expert Working Group 2005). The system suitability (i.e., repeatability of retention times and areas, number of theoretical plates, resolution, tailing factor), precision, and linearity were evaluated during method validation as described by [14]. All sample solutions were stored in amber glass bottles (protected from light) and analysed directly without any dilution; each sample was measured in triplicate.

4.3. Delivered Dose

The delivered dose and delivered dose rate of nebulised FUR were assessed according to the methods described in Ph. Eur. (2.9.44). The Aerogen Solo VMN was attached to an Aerogen Ultra adapter connected to a low-pressure and low-volume filter (Clear-Guard 3 Breathing Filter, Intersurgical Ltd., Wokingham, United Kingdom), which was further connected to a breathing simulator (Figure 2). The adapter was equipped with one-way flap valves to alternate airflow between inspiration and expiration. The nebuliser was filled with 4 mL of the commercial FUR Kabi 20 mg/2 mL solution (2 ampoules).

The breathing simulator operated with a sinusoidal breathing pattern, a tidal volume of 500 mL, and a breathing frequency of 15 min^{-1} , in agreement with Ph. Eur. The production of aerosol began concurrently with the simulated breathing process. After a one-minute nebulisation interval, the apparatus filter was replaced. This process continued until the entire dose in the nebuliser was aerosolised. All used filters were immersed in methanol to extract the deposited FUR; samples were then analysed by HPLC.

Figure 4: Measurement of the delivered dose.

4.4. Aerodynamic Particle Size Distribution

An Andersen Cascade Impactor (ACI) was used to analyse the aerodynamic particle size distribution. The ACI was cooled to 5 °C to prevent particle evaporation, as recommended by Ph. Eur. (2.9.44). A custom-moulded adapter for the Aerogen Ultra mouthpiece was placed at the inlet of the ACI induction port. The outlet of the ACI was connected to a vacuum pump through a TSI 4040 flow meter (TSI Inc., Minnesota, USA). The Aerogen Solo nebuliser was connected to the assembly through the Aerogen Ultra adapter. The sampling duration was one minute at a flow rate of 28.3 L·min⁻¹. After sampling, each stage of the ACI was washed with methanol to extract the deposited FUR; the samples were analysed by HPLC. The fine particle fraction (FPF), mass median aerodynamic diameter (MMAD), and geometric standard deviation (GSD) were calculated from the measured FUR mass in each ACI stage.

4.5. Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry Modelling

To provide a probabilistic assessment of regional aerosol deposition, the Multiple-Path Particle Dosimetry (MPPD) model (Version 3.04, Applied Research Associates, Inc., Raleigh, NC, USA) was employed. This model calculates the deposition probability of particles using a mechanistic approach based on the single-path and multiple-path algorithms described by [15] and [16]. It enables rapid estimation of deposited dose in human and animal airways under various breathing conditions, although it relies on empirical efficiency functions rather than solving the full three-dimensional (3D) flow field.

The simulation was configured using the "Human (Limited)" lung geometry, which utilises the Yeh and Schum 5-Lobe model [17] to account for lobar asymmetry. The Functional Residual Capacity (FRC) was scaled to 3300 mL (standard adult male). The input parameters were matched to the experimental boundary conditions as follows:

- Aerosol Properties: MMAD of 3.03 µm and GSD of 1.80.
- Breathing Parameters: To simulate the dyspnoea breathing pattern used in the *in vitro* and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) studies, the model was set to oral breathing with a tidal volume of 1390 mL and a breathing frequency of 28.6 min⁻¹ [18]. The inspiratory fraction was set to 0.2 (inhalation time 0.42 s), resulting in a mean inspiratory flow rate of approximately 3.3 L·s⁻¹.
- The inhalability adjustment was enabled to account for the aspiration efficiency at the mouth during high-flow oral breathing.

4.6. Aerosol Deposition in Airway Replica

The deposition measurements were conducted using a realistic model of human respiratory airways, the development and dimensions of which were thoroughly described by Lizal et al. [19]. The model was created by combining multiple geometries and included airways from the oral cavity extending to the 7th generation of tracheobronchial branching (generations G0–G7). The oral cavity was moulded from a dental impression of a volunteer at the Lovelace Respiratory Research Institute (Albuquerque, NM, USA) and is referred to as 'cast A' in [20]. The tracheobronchial tree was derived from the digital reference model of Schmidt et al. [21], which was based on CT scans from a cadaver. To facilitate the numerical simulations and experiments, cylindrical inlet and funnel-like outlet segments were added to allow the prescription of boundary conditions or the connection of tubing.

The resulting digital model has ten outlets, with two in each lobe, and was physically segmented into key geometric airway parts, such as the trachea or the first bifurcation (Figure 3). To ensure clarity

across the different modelling approaches, specific terminology is used consistently throughout this study. The airway replica is divided into discrete *segments* based on manufacturing requirements and branching topology. These physical *segments* are numbered from top to bottom (1–22), with the oral cavity designated as Segment 1, the trachea as Segment 2, and so on (see Figure 3). These segments correspond to anatomical airway *generations* (G) according to the Weibel model [22]. While the segments represent the building blocks of the physical and computational domain, the generations denote the depth within the tracheobronchial tree (G0–G7). Finally, the term *stage* is reserved exclusively for the *stages* of the ACI, corresponding to specific aerodynamic particle size fractions (Figure 6).

For the purpose of deposition experiments, a 3 mm-thick shell was created around the digital geometry. Flanges with screws or bayonet joints were integrated between the segments to enable model assembly. The segments were fabricated on a Stratasys J850 printer (Stratasys, Minnesota, USA) using VeroClear material with an accuracy of 0.015 mm and a layer thickness of 14 μm . Prior to each experiment, the assembled replica was leak-tested, and any detected leaks were sealed using silicone sealant.

Figure 5: The schematic of the digital model (left) and experimental replica (right). The model is segmented and has two outlets per lobe; LUL denotes the left upper lobe, LLL denotes the left lower lobe, RUL denotes the right upper lobe, RML denotes the right middle lobe, and RLL denotes the right lower lobe.

The breathing parameters used in this study were based on the work of O'Donnell et al. (2009), who reported the breathing patterns of COPD patients during dyspnoea. The specific parameters included a breathing frequency of 28.6 min^{-1} , a tidal volume of 1.39 L, and an inspiratory-to-expiratory (I:E) ratio of 1:4. The breathing profile (Figure 4) was reconstructed based on the shape of the breathing cycle and the flow rate distribution between the lung lobes measured and reported by [23]. The breathing simulator used in the experimental part of the study consisted of five pistons with programmable movement. Each piston corresponded to one lung lobe and moved according to the defined profile. Consequently, the ten outlets of the airway replica (two per lobe) were connected to the corresponding five pistons of the simulator.

Figure 6: The reconstructed lobar breathing profiles of a dyspnoea patient

The segmented airway replica was assembled and connected to the breathing simulator (Figure 5), and all connections were sealed to prevent leaks. The replica was cooled to 5 °C to avoid droplet evaporation and to enable comparison with the ACI data. Nitrocellulose membrane filters (MF-Millipore™, pore size of 0.45 μm, diameter of 25 mm) were placed in filter holders and connected to each outlet of the airway replica to collect aerosol passing through the model's branching levels. The model was connected to the inspiratory branches of the breathing simulator. Only inspiration was directed through the airway replica; expiration was vented in front of the Aerogen Ultra mouthpiece to prevent droplet accumulation and ensure realistic aerosol properties. The nebuliser was filled with 4 mL of FUR preparation (2 ampoules) and connected to the Aerogen Ultra adapter. The sampling duration consisted of 100 breathing cycles, during which the nebuliser generated aerosol continuously. After exposure, the airway model was disassembled, the deposited aerosol was extracted from the surfaces of each segment using methanol, and samples were analysed by HPLC to determine the mass fraction of FUR deposited in each segment.

Figure 7: The scheme of the experimental setup used for deposition measurements

4.7. Setup of the Computational Simulation

Numerical simulations using the CFD approach were performed in the commercial solver Simcenter Star-CCM+ v2210 Build 17.06.007. The simulation was carried out in three stages to replicate the conditions of the *in vitro* experiment as closely as possible. The first stage represented the inspiratory part of the respiratory cycle. During this phase, particles were injected into the domain at uniform time intervals, with diameters corresponding to the experimentally determined aerodynamic particle size distribution. Since the *in vitro* setup diverted expiratory flow away from the airway replica (as described in Section 2.6), the second stage of the simulation was defined as a period of zero airflow (simulating a breath hold within the model volume). During this stage, particle injection was disabled to mimic the absence of incoming aerosol during the expiratory phase. The duration of this stage corresponded to the expiratory time of the breathing cycle. Finally, because a non-negligible number of particles remained suspended in the domain after the second stage, a third stage consisting of a second inspiratory cycle was performed to allow the remaining particles to settle or exit the domain.

The geometry of the physical model used in the experiment was discretised using a computational mesh consisting of 10.93 million elements. The volume mesh was constructed using polyhedral cells, while the boundary layer was resolved using ten layers of prismatic elements. The base cell size was set to 0.8 mm, based on the Taylor microscale calculated at peak flow velocity. To ensure accurate near-wall flow resolution, the first cell height was adjusted to satisfy the condition $y^+ < 1$. A mesh independence study was performed following the methodology described by Farkas et al. [24] to ensure that the results were not dependent on the grid resolution.

The calculation was solved as unsteady with an adaptive time step length to satisfy the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy condition ($CFL \leq 1$). Turbulence was modelled using LES with the Wall-Adapting Local Eddy-viscosity (WALE) subgrid-scale model [25]. The conservation of mass and momentum was resolved using a segregated flow solver.

The particle deposition was solved by the multiphase Euler-Lagrangian approach, which solves the equation of motion for a spherical particle moving within the Eulerian continuum. The particle sizes were sampled based on the cumulative distribution function measured by ACI (as described in Section 2.4). The interaction between the continuous and dispersed phases was modelled using one-way coupling. The forces acting on the particles included gravity, the drag force calculated using the Schiller-Naumann correlation [26], and the pressure gradient force. The particles were injected into the domain via 100 injection points uniformly distributed across the inlet of the mouthpiece adapter. During the inspiratory phase, 1.2 million particles were injected, and their transport and deposition were subsequently tracked through the remaining simulation phases.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Frantisek Lizal: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Visualisation; Supervision; Writing -original draft; Writing - review & editing

Miloslav Belka: Investigation; Methodology; Visualisation; Writing - review & editing

Ondrej Misik: Investigation; Methodology; Writing - review & editing

Zdenka Sklupalova: Conceptualisation; Writing - review & editing

Jakub Elcner: Investigation; Visualisation, Writing - review & editing

Ludmila Matysova: Investigation; Writing - review & editing

Michal Svarc: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Writing - review & editing

Vladimir Koblizek: Conceptualisation; Methodology; Supervision; Writing - review & editing

Funding declaration

This publication was supported by the Czech Science Foundation grant No. 25-16971S and by the project "Mechanical Engineering of Biological and Bio-inspired Systems", funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004634 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. The work of MŠ and VK was supported by the Czech Ministry of Health via AZV agency the inhalation treatment prospective project: AZV NW 25-09-00434. Inhaled furosemide clinical study (INFURO) is supported by Masaryk University Brno, CZECRIN LM2023049 and Charles University Prague, Cooperatio program – research area INDI.

Data Availability Statement: The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are available in the Zenodo repository, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18508754>.

References

1. Maddocks, M., Lovell, N., Booth, S., Man, W. D.-C. & Higginson, I. J. Palliative care and management of troublesome symptoms for people with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Lancet* **390**, 988–1002 (2017).
2. Parshall, M. B. *et al.* An Official American Thoracic Society Statement: Update on the Mechanisms, Assessment, and Management of Dyspnea. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* **185**, 435–452 (2012).

3. Ong, K.-C., Kor, A.-C., Chong, W.-F., Earnest, A. & Wang, Y.-T. Effects of Inhaled Furosemide on Exertional Dyspnea in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* **169**, 1028–1033 (2004).
4. Nishino, T., Ide, T., Sudo, T. & Sato, J. Inhaled Furosemide Greatly Alleviates the Sensation of Experimentally Induced Dyspnea. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* **161**, 1963–1967 (2000).
5. Jensen, D., Amjadi, K., Harris-McAllister, V., Webb, K. A. & O'Donnell, D. E. Mechanisms of dyspnoea relief and improved exercise endurance after furosemide inhalation in COPD. *Thorax* **63**, 606–613 (2008).
6. Sierra-Johnson, J. Inhaled furosemide: a whole new mechanism of action. *Med Hypotheses* **58**, 529–530 (2002).
7. Sudo, T., Hayashi, F. & Nishino, T. Responses of Tracheobronchial Receptors to Inhaled Furosemide in Anesthetized Rats. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med* **162**, 971–975 (2000).
8. Moosavi, S. H. *et al.* Effect of inhaled furosemide on air hunger induced in healthy humans. *Respir Physiol Neurobiol* **156**, 1–8 (2007).
9. Hallowell, R. W., Schwartzstein, R., O'Donnell, C. R., Sheridan, A. & Banzett, R. B. Controlled Delivery of 80 mg Aerosol Furosemide Does Not Achieve Consistent Dyspnea Relief in Patients. *Lung* **198**, 113–120 (2020).
10. Barnes, P. J. *et al.* Barriers to new drug development in respiratory disease. *European Respiratory Journal* **45**, 1197–1207 (2015).
11. Council of Europe. *European Pharmacopoeia*. (Council of Europe, Strasbourg, 2023).
12. Corcoran, T. E. & Chigier, N. Characterization of the laryngeal jet using phase Doppler interferometry. *Journal of Aerosol Medicine-Deposition Clearance and Effects in the Lung* **13**, 125–137 (2000).
13. Misik, O. *et al.* Nebulization and *In Vitro* Upper Airway Deposition of Liposomal Carrier Systems. *Mol. Pharm.* **21**, 1848–1860 (2024).

14. Zahalka, L., Klovrvzova, S., Matysova, L., Sklubalova, Z. & Solich, P. Furosemide ethanol-free oral solutions for paediatric use: formulation, HPLC method and stability study. *Eur. J. Hosp. Pharm.* **25**, 144–149 (2018).
15. Anjilvel, S. & Asgharian, B. A Multiple-Path Model of Particle Deposition in the Rat Lung. *Fundamental and Applied Toxicology* **28**, 41–50 (1995).
16. Freijer, J. *et al.* Multiple Path Particle Deposition Model (MPPDep Version 1.11). A model for human and rat airway particle deposition. (1999).
17. Yeh, H.-C. & Schum, G. M. Models of human lung airways and their application to inhaled particle deposition. *Bulletin of Mathematical Biology* **42**, 461–480 (1980).
18. O'Donnell, D. E., Ora, J., Webb, K. A., Laveneziana, P. & Jensen, D. Mechanisms of activity-related dyspnea in pulmonary diseases. *Respiratory Physiology & Neurobiology* **167**, 116–132 (2009).
19. Lizal, F., Elcner, J., Hopke, P. K., Jedelsky, J. & Jicha, M. Development of a realistic human airway model. *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers Part H-Journal of Engineering in Medicine* **226**, 197–207 (2012).
20. Su, W.-C. & Cheng, Y. S. Fiber Deposition Pattern in Two Human Respiratory Tract Replicas. *Inhalation Toxicology* **18**, 749–760 (2006).
21. Schmidt, A. *et al.* A digital reference model of the human bronchial tree. *Comput. Med. Imaging Graph.* **28**, 203–211 (2004).
22. Weibel, E. *Morphometry of the Human Lung*. (Springer Verlag and Academic Press, Berlin, New York, 1963).
23. Jahani, N. *et al.* Assessment of regional ventilation and deformation using 4D-CT imaging for healthy human lungs during tidal breathing. *J Appl Physiol* **119**, 1064–1074 (2015).
24. Farkas, A., Lizal, F., Elcner, J., Jedelsky, J. & Jicha, M. Numerical simulation of fibre deposition in oral and large bronchial airways in comparison with experiments. *J Aerosol Sci* **136**, 1–14 (2019).

25. Nicoud, F. & Ducros, F. Subgrid-Scale Stress Modelling Based on the Square of the Velocity Gradient Tensor. *Flow, Turbulence and Combustion* **62**, 183–200 (1999).
26. Schiller, L. Über die grundlegenden Berechnungen bei der Schwerkraftaufbereitung. *Z. Ver. Dtsch. Ing.* **77**, 318–320 (1933).
27. Hickey, A. J. *Inhalation Aerosols: Physical and Biological Basis for Therapy*. (CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2006).
28. Nelson, H. S. Inhalation devices, delivery systems, and patient technique. *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology* **117**, 606–612 (2016).
29. Ghanem, R. *et al.* The (re)emergence of aerosol delivery: Treatment of pulmonary diseases and its clinical challenges. *J Control Release* **379**, 421–439 (2025).
30. Mekonnen, T., Cai, X., Burchell, C., Gholizadeh, H. & Cheng, S. A review of upper airway physiology relevant to the delivery and deposition of inhalation aerosols. *Advanced Drug Delivery Reviews* **191**, 114530 (2022).
31. Koullapis, P. *et al.* Regional aerosol deposition in the human airways: The SimInhale benchmark case and a critical assessment of in silico methods. *European Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences* **113**, 77–94 (2018).
32. Matida, E. A., Finlay, W. H., Lange, C. F. & Grgic, B. Improved numerical simulation of aerosol deposition in an idealized mouth-throat. *Journal of Aerosol Science* **35**, 1–19 (2004).
33. Kuprat, A. P. *et al.* Efficient bi-directional coupling of 3D computational fluid-particle dynamics and 1D Multiple Path Particle Dosimetry lung models for multiscale modeling of aerosol dosimetry. *Journal of Aerosol Science* **151**, 105647 (2021).
34. Panahi, Y. *et al.* Furosemide Inhalation in Dyspnea of Mustard Gas-Exposed Patients: A Triple-Blind Randomized Study. *Inhalation Toxicology* **20**, 873–877 (2008).
35. Nikolaou, M. *et al.* Superparamagnetic electrospun microrods for magnetically-guided pulmonary drug delivery with magnetic heating. *Materials Science and Engineering: C* **126**, 112117 (2021).

36. Motiei, M. *et al.* Engineering of inhalable nano-in-microparticles for co-delivery of small molecules and miRNAs. *Discov. Nano.* **18**, 38 (2023).

37. Mestre-Ferrandiz, J., Sussex, J. & Towse, A. *The R&D Cost of a New Medicine.* (Office of Health Economics, London, 2012).

Figure Legends:

Figure 1: Experimental setup for confirmation of FUR compatibility with VMN.

Figure 2: Measurement of the delivered dose.

Figure 3: The schematic of the digital model (left) and experimental replica (right). The model is segmented and has two outlets per lobe; LUL denotes the left upper lobe, LLL denotes the left lower lobe, RUL denotes the right upper lobe, RML denotes the right middle lobe, and RLL denotes the right lower lobe.

Figure 4: The reconstructed lobar breathing profiles of a dyspnoea patient.

Figure 5: The scheme of the experimental setup used for deposition measurements.

Figure 6: The mass aerodynamic particle size distribution of nebulised FUR preparation given by the Andersen cascade impactor with 7 stages.

Figure 7: The comparison of deposition fraction in the airway replica obtained by experiment (EXP) and by CFD simulations. Error bars represent standard deviations.

Figure 8: Comparison of the lobar deposition fraction distribution of particles obtained by experiment (EXP), and simulations by CFD (LES) and MPPD. Error bars represent standard deviations of experimental results.